

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Design And Development of Sublingual Films Incorporating R-HCL And Vitamin D-Loaded NLCS

Sweta Jaiswal, Surendra Dangi*, Dr. Bhaskar Kumar Gupta, Rajni Dubey

School of Pharmacy and Research People's University, Bhopal (M.P.) 462037, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 June 2025

Keywords:

Osteoporosis,
Nanostructured Lipid
Carriers, Postmenopausal
Osteoporosis, Sublingual
Films, Osteoclasts and
Osteoblasts

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15710998

ABSTRACT

Osteoporosis, particularly postmenopausal (Type I), is a progressive bone disorder characterized by reduced bone density and increased fracture risk, primarily due to estrogen deficiency. Raloxifene Hydrochloride (R-HCl), a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM), offers bone-protective effects without adversely impacting the uterus or breast. However, its low solubility and poor oral bioavailability limit therapeutic effectiveness. This study aimed to enhance the solubility and permeability of R-HCl by formulating nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) co-loaded with Vitamin D (Vit D), a vital supplement in bone health, using the micro-emulsification technique followed by high-speed homogenization. The optimized NLCs demonstrated a mean particle size below 300 nm, a narrow polydispersity index (0.192), and a negative zeta potential (-0.69 mV), indicating uniformity and stability. Entrapment efficiency was observed at 91.41% for R-HCl and 79.56% for Vit D, with corresponding drug content values of 85.76% and 80.24%. Characterization by DSC and FTIR confirmed stable drug incorporation, while HRTEM revealed spherical morphology. These NLCs were incorporated into sublingual films prepared using HPMC and glycerol, offering improved bioavailability and bypassing first-pass metabolism. The films exhibited favorable organoleptic properties, rapid disintegration, high tensile strength (5.453 N/mm²), uniform weight, and surface pH of 6.8—comparable to buccal pH—ensuring mucosal compatibility. Drug content per cm² was 89.43% (R-HCl) and 84.67% (Vit D), with efficient in vitro drug release. This study highlights the successful development of R-HCl and Vit D-loaded NLCs in film form as a promising and effective approach for managing postmenopausal osteoporosis.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoporosis is a chronic bone condition marked by a progressive reduction in bone mineral density

***Corresponding Author:** Surendra Dangi

Address: School of Pharmacy and Research People's University, Bhopal (M.P.) 462037, India.

Email ✉: surdangi89@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

(BMD) and the deterioration of bone microarchitecture, which significantly raises the risk of fractures. It poses a serious public health concern, especially among older adults. In the United States, about 10.3% of individuals over the age of 50 are diagnosed with osteoporosis. The condition becomes increasingly prevalent with age and shows a notable gender disparity approximately 77.1% of women over 80 years old are affected, compared to 46.3% of men. This difference is largely attributed to hormonal changes, particularly the decline in estrogen levels following menopause, which accelerates the process of bone breakdown. Bone remodeling is a continuous and dynamic process involving the coordinated actions of two types of cells: osteoclasts, which break down bone, and osteoblasts, which build new bone. When this equilibrium is disturbed—due to factors such as aging, hormonal imbalances, or long-term use of medications like glucocorticoids—bone mass decreases, making bones more brittle and susceptible to fractures. Estrogen plays a critical role in bone metabolism by modulating osteoclast activity through the RANK/RANKL/OPG signaling pathway. A deficiency in estrogen, commonly seen in postmenopausal women, leads

to heightened osteoclast activity and subsequent bone loss. Osteoporosis is typically diagnosed using a bone mineral density scan, most often via dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA). A T-score of -2.5 or lower is indicative of osteoporosis. Management of the condition involves a combination of drug therapies and lifestyle modifications aimed at reducing the likelihood of fractures. Although estrogen replacement therapy (ERT) has traditionally been a central treatment option, its potential health risks have prompted the exploration of safer alternatives, such as selective estrogen receptor modulators (SERMs), with Raloxifene hydrochloride (R-HCl) being one of the most widely studied agents. Recently, advancements in nanotechnology have led to the development of novel drug delivery systems, including Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs), which have shown promise in improving the bioavailability and therapeutic potential of R-HCl. These innovative approaches may offer more efficient and safer treatment options for managing postmenopausal osteoporosis, minimizing systemic side effects while enhancing clinical outcomes. [1-3]

Materials and Equipment's

Table 1: Various chemicals and reagents used in research work

S. No.	Material Source (M/S)	Material Source (M/S)
1.	Acetonitrile	Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
2.	Capryol 90	Gattefosse, Paramus, SAS, France
3.	Castor oil	Fisher Scientific
4.	Chloroform	Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
5.	Compritol® 888 ATO	Gattefosse, Paramus, SAS, France
6.	Disodium hydrogen phosphate	Thermo Fischer Scientific, Mumbai, India
7.	EDTA vials	CurDia Lifesciences Pvt. Ltd., Haryana
8.	Glycerol	HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.
9.	Glyceryl monostearate	Central Drug House Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi, India
10.	Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose K4M	Panacea BioTec, Lalru, Punjab
11.	Isopropyl myristate	Avra Synthesis Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad
12.	Labrafac	Gattefosse, Paramus, SAS, France
13.	Labrafill	Gattefosse, Paramus, SAS, France
14.	Mannitol	Fisher Scientific

15.	Methanol LR Grade	Fischer Scientific, Mumbai, India
16.	Oleic acid	Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
17.	Ortho-phosphoric acid	Paskem Fine Chem Pvt Ltd, India
18.	Polysorbate 20	Fisher Scientific
19.	Polysorbate 80	Fisher Scientific
20.	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate	Thermo Fischer Scientific, Mumbai, India
21.	R-HCl	Panacea BioTec, Lalru, Punjab
22.	Sodium chloride (NaCl)	Rankem Laboratories, New Delhi, India
23.	Sodium hydroxide	Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
24.	Stearic acid	S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai, India
25.	Vit D3	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany)

Table 2: List of various equipment items employed during the research work

S. No.	Equipment	Manufacturer (M/S)
1.	Centrifuge	Rajendra Electrical Industries Ltd. Vasai, India
2.	Deep freezer (CHF400B, 18°C to - 22°C)	Remi Elektrotechnik Ltd, Mumbai, India
3.	Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Q20)	TA Instruments, Detroit, USA
4.	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR; Spectrum RX1)	Perkin Elmer, Massachusetts, USA
5.	HR-TEM	JEOL-JEM 2100 Plus
6.	Lab water purification System	Evoqua, USA
7.	Particle size and zeta potential analyzer	Malvern, Worcestershire, UK
8.	pH meter	Pico+, Lab India, Mumbai, India
9.	UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	SHIMADZU UV – 1800
10.	Water bath (W19)	Haake, India
11.	Water bath shaker (NSW 133)	Narang Scientific works, New Delhi, India
12.	Weighing balance	Shimadzu, Japan

Experimental Work

R-HCl analysis via UV spectrophotometric method

Standard plot of R-HCl in various solvents: UV spectroscopy using methanol, chloroform:methanol (1:1), and PBS pH 7.4 quantified drug concentration and determined extinction coefficients during microemulsion development and NLC characterization through standard plots.

Standard plot in methanol: R-HCl was dissolved in methanol to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock, then diluted (1–10 µg/ml). Absorbance at 284 nm was

measured, and specific absorbance calculated using the trendline equation.

Standard plot in chloroform: methanol (1:1):

R-HCl was dissolved in chloroform:methanol (1:1) to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock, diluted (1–10 µg/ml), analyzed at 297.5 nm, and specific absorbance calculated using the trendline equation.

Standard plot in PBS pH 7.4: R-HCl was dissolved in PBS (pH 7.4) to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock, diluted (1–10 µg/ml), analyzed at 289 nm, and specific absorbance calculated using the trendline equation. ^[4-7]

Validation of the analytical method

Linearity: Linearity was assessed for R-HCl (1–10 µg/ml) in methanol, chloroform:methanol (1:1), and PBS using six repeated spectrophotometric analyses.

Accuracy: Accuracy of R-HCl in methanol was evaluated by comparing experimental and nominal concentrations, following US-FDA (2018) ±15% acceptance criteria.

Precision: Precision was evaluated by analyzing 10 µg/ml R-HCl in different solvents (n=6), ensuring results met US-FDA (2018) ±15% criteria.

Inter and intra-day variability: Inter- and intra-day variability of R-HCl in methanol was analyzed at set intervals, assessing accuracy and precision per US-FDA (2018) guidelines (n=3).

Vit D Analysis via UV Spectrophotometric Method

Standard plot of Vit D in various solvents: A UV spectroscopy method using various solvents was developed to quantify Vitamin D during microemulsion and NLC characterization, determining extinction coefficients from standard plots prepared in triplicate.

Standard plot in methanol: Vitamin D was dissolved in methanol to create a 100 µg/ml stock, diluted (1–20 µg/ml), analyzed at 265 nm, and specific absorbance calculated using the trendline equation.

Standard plot in chloroform: methanol (1:1): Vitamin D was dissolved in chloroform: methanol (1:1) to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock, diluted (1–20 µg/ml), analyzed at 265 nm, and specific absorbance determined via trendline equation.

Standard plot in PBS pH 7.4: Vitamin D was dissolved in PBS (pH 7.4) to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock, diluted (1–20 µg/ml), analyzed at 265 nm, and specific absorbance calculated using the trendline equation.

Validation of the Analytical Method

Linearity: Linearity of Vitamin D (1–20 µg/ml) was evaluated in methanol, chloroform: methanol (1:1), and PBS (pH 7.4) across six replicates.

Accuracy: Accuracy of Vitamin D in methanol was evaluated by comparing experimental and nominal values (1–20 µg/ml) per US-FDA (2018) ±15% criteria.

Precision: Precision of 20 µg/ml Vitamin D in different solvents (n=6) was analyzed, ensuring results met US-FDA (2018) ±15% acceptance criteria.

Inter and intra-day variability: Inter- and intra-day variability of Vitamin D in methanol was assessed at set intervals (n=3) following US-FDA (2018) precision and accuracy guidelines.

Solubility Studies

Solubility in oils and surfactants: This study evaluated R-HCl solubility in various oils and surfactants. After 24-hour mixing and centrifugation, supernatants were diluted and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 284 nm.

Solubility in solid lipids: Solid lipid selection was based on R-HCl solubility observed visually in molten lipids—Compritol 888 ATO®, stearic acid, and GMS—heated in a water bath.

Construction of ternary phase diagram

NLC formulation began with a pseudo-ternary phase diagram using various surfactant ratios.

Lipid phases were heated, mixed, titrated with water, stirred at 80°C, and visually assessed for transparency. The identical methodology was replicated subsequent to the introduction of lipids in summary.

- Pre-weighed test tubes were utilised to prepare mixtures of the lipid phase and surfactant phase at various ratios (w/w) ranging from 10:0 to 0:10.
- The lipid phase was melted by heating above its melting point, then combined with a pre-heated surfactant phase under gentle stirring to form a uniform mixture. This was gradually titrated with distilled water and stirred at 60°C until equilibrium. Transparency was visually inspected, and TriDraw software was used to construct a pseudo-ternary diagram to identify optimal microemulsion regions.

Characterization of microemulsion: Freeze-thaw cycling involves repeatedly freezing and thawing water. The selected microemulsion series underwent freeze-thaw cycles between 4°C and 40°C for 24 hours each, over a one-week period. This process aimed to observe any physical instabilities, such as phase separation or precipitation, to assess the stability of the

microemulsion formulations under varying temperature conditions. [8-10]

Formulation Studies

Preparation of microemulsion: An o/w microemulsion containing R-HCl and Vit D was prepared through a process involving the melting of solid lipid, the addition of liquid lipid, and the subsequent solubilization of the drug in the resulting mixture to form the lipid phase. The aqueous phase consisted of a combination of surfactant, co-surfactant, and water. The two phases were subjected to a temperature higher than the melting point of the solid lipid and subsequently blended to yield a heated microemulsion.

Preparation of NLCS: NLCs were prepared using the micro-emulsification technique with Compritol® 888 ATO as the solid lipid and oleic acid as the liquid lipid. Drug (30 mg R-HCl and 200 µL Vit D) was added to the melted lipid phase. The aqueous phase, containing Tween 80 and Capryol 90, was heated and mixed with the lipid phase. The microemulsion was stirred at 90°C, then cooled in chilled water and homogenized. Blank NLCs were prepared similarly, without drug addition. Formulations were stored below 25°C.

Table 3: The various trial batches of NLCs

Formulation Code	RHCL (mg)	Vit D (µL)	Compritol 888 (mg)	Oleic Acid (mg)	Tween 80 (mg)	Capryol 90 (mg)	Water (mg)	Homo Time	Homo Speed
N1	20	50	700	300	800	3200	5000	-	-
N2	10	100	700	300	1000	4000	4000	15	13000
N3	20	150	700	300	1200	4800	3000	15	13000
N4	20	175	900	100	1100	4400	3500	15	15000
N5	10	220	700	300	1000	4000	4000	15	13000
N6	10	250	700	300	1000	4000	4000	20	13000
N7	15	200	800	200	1100	4400	3500	15	15000
N8	10	300	900	100	1400	5600	4000	10	15000

Note* Turbid microemulsion was obtained and so NLCs were not prepared.

The N7 formulation demonstrated consistent particle size, high entrapment efficiency, and stability with minimal surfactant. After optimization, N7 was selected for further evaluation. The study assessed ingredient levels, homogenization time, and speed for improving drug incorporation into NLCs, followed by film production.

Preparation of Sublingual Film

Sublingual films improve bioavailability by bypassing first-pass metabolism, utilizing water-

soluble polymers like HPMC, which act as emulsifiers, stabilizers, and film formers. HPMC films are transparent, odorless, stable, biodegradable, and non-toxic. To prepare fast-dissolving films, varying amounts of HPMC K4M were immersed in phosphate-buffered saline, glycerol added, and agitated at 60°C. The mixture was dissolved in methanol and water, followed by stirring and the addition of hot water to adjust viscosity. The process was optimized by varying film compositions and preparation parameters.[11-12]

Table 4: Compositions and variables for the preparation of film

Formulation code	HPMC (gm)	Glycerol (gm)	PBS pH 7.4 (ml)	Water (ml)	NLCs dispersion (mg)	Methanol (ml)	Stirring Time (hr)	Observation
F1	8	2	100	-	15	-	3	Too thick to pour
F2	1.5	2	50	-	-	-	3	Sticky film
F3	0.4	2	25	-	-	-	4	Immediate gelling
F4	0.4	1	-	-	1	5	2	Immediate gelling
F5	1.6	0.4	-	5	2	12	2	Very thin film
F6	0.2	0.1	-	-	10	-	2	Good thickness
F7	0.7	0.3	-	12	35	-	1	Good
F8	1	0.5	-	5	45	-	1	Viscous formulation, hard to pour

Figure 1: Solvent casting in the petri-plate

Formulations F6 and F7 were selected for their solution uniformity. F6 was prepared using the solvent evaporation technique with HPMC and glycerol, stirred for 2 hours, and cast into a 10 cm petri dish. F7 was developed using 2% w/v HPMC

K4M and 1% w/v glycerol, stirred for 2 hours with gradual hot water addition. The solution was spread using a Wasag Model 288 Applicator (gap: 900 μm) and dried at room temperature for 24 hours using a TDP/ODF film forming system.

Figure 2: Solvent Casting on Film Former Machine

The film was appropriately trimmed to obtain films with an area of 1 square centimeter each.

Subsequently, these films were employed to ascertain additional characteristics.

Figure 3: Sublingual film of area 1cm²

Characterization of Selected NLC Formulation

Particle size, Polydispersity index (PDI) and Zeta potential:

One-milliliter aliquots were extracted from the non-ionic liquid crystal dispersion and subsequently diluted with 20 millilitres of distilled water. The mixture was then stirred for three minutes. Subsequently, a diluted dispersion of 1 mL was utilised for particle size analysis through dynamic light scattering with a Malvern Zetasizer.

Total drug content (TDC): To determine the TDC of NLC dispersion containing R-HCl and Vit D, 1 ml was disrupted with chloroform:methanol (1:1), diluted to 10 ml, sonicated for 1 hour, and filtered.

Entrapment efficiency (EE): The efficiency of the R-HCl and Vit D dispersion that was prepared was assessed through the use of a dialysis membrane with a pore size of 2.4 nm and a molecular weight cutoff range of 12–14 Kda. The spectrophotometric analysis of drug release into the receptor or release medium was conducted at 284 nm and 265 nm for R-HCl and Vit D respectively using suitable dilutions.

The calculation of entrapment efficiency was performed using equation (1).

$$\frac{\text{Entrapped Drug Content (mg)}}{\text{Total Drug Content (mg)}} \times 100$$

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC):

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed using DSC 60, analyzing samples from 25–300 °C at 10 °C/min to record thermograms via specialized software after proper sealing.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

FTIR analysis using Shimadzu FTIR 8400S identified drug-lipid interactions. Samples were pelletized with KBr, and spectra were recorded from 4000–400 cm⁻¹ to study individual and combined formulation components.

Characterization of Film

pH: Surface pH was measured after swelling the film in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) for 2 hours using a pH meter.

Total drug content: Drug content uniformity was evaluated by dissolving the film in buffer,

filtering, and analyzing R-HCl and Vit D spectrophotometrically.

Thickness: The measurement of film thickness was conducted at three distinct locations using a digital vernier calliper. Subsequently, the arithmetic average was documented.

Weight variation: Weight variation was assessed by randomly selecting and individually weighing three films from each batch using a digital balance.

Tensile strength: Tensile strength was measured using an Instron tester by stretching films between clamps 2 cm apart until breakage, and calculating the maximum force endured using the standard tensile strength formula.

Disintegration time: As per CDER, orally disintegrating tablets must disintegrate within 30 seconds, a standard also applied to fast-dissolving films, typically disintegrating within 5–30 seconds using pharmacopoeial apparatus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UV-Vis Analysis and Preformulation of R-HCl: Standard plots for R-HCl were generated in three different solvents: methanol, chloroform: methanol (1:1), and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS): methanol with a pH of 7.4. The resulting standard plots were then analysed. Table 5 provides information on the linearity range, and R² for the standard plots of R-HCl.

$$\text{Tensile strength (N/mm}^2\text{)} = \frac{\text{Force at break}}{\text{Initial cross sectional area}}$$

Table 5: λ_{max} and extinction coefficient of R-HCl in various solvents in concentration range (1- 10 g/ml)

Solvent	Linearity Range (µg/ml)	λ _{max} (nm)	E1% 1cm (gm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ dl)	R ₂
Methanol	1-10	284	1317	0.9988
Chloroform: methanol (1:1)	1-10	297.5	526	0.9990
PBS (pH-7.4): Methanol	1-10	286	666	0.9954

Figure 4: Calibration curve of R-HCl in methanol with concentration range (1-10 µg/ml)

Figure 5: Calibration curve of R-HCl in chloroform: methanol (1:1) with concentration range (1-10µg/ml)

Figure 6: Calibration curve of R-HCl in buffer (PBS 7.4): methanol (1:1) with concentration range (1-10µg/ml)

Validation of Analytical Method

Linearity: Solutions of varying concentrations (1-10 µg/mL) of R-HCl were prepared in respective solvents and their absorbance was measured (n=6). The results **Figure 15, 16** and **17** showed a linear relationship between concentration and corresponding absorbance values upon repeated observations.

Accuracy: Accuracy of the UV spectrophotometric method of analysis for R-HCl

in the methanol was assessed. Accuracy of $\pm 15\%$ is considered to be satisfactory as per the US-FDA guidelines (2018), and the values obtained presently were found to fall within these limits, thus validating the test.

Precision: The UV spectrophotometric method of analysis for R-HCl was sufficiently precise as indicated by a small S.D ≤ 0.0137 in the repetitive determinations of the same concentration (10 µg/mL) of R-HCl in different solvents. The results

were within the limits defined by US-FDA guidelines (2018) ($\leq 15\%$).

Inter- and intra-day variability: Different concentrations of the drug were prepared in methanol and analysed at intervals of 0, 6, 24,

36,48 hours. The inter- and intra-day variability in precision and accuracy was found to be in accordance with US-FDA guidelines (2018) ($\leq 15\%$) average inter and intraday variability was reported as shown in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Variability of UV spectrophotometric technique for R-HCl in methanol measurement between and within days.

Intra-Day Variability			
Nominal concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Precision (S.D)	% Accuracy
1	0.9	0.015	89.76
5	4.25	0.019	85.04
10	8.65	0.004	86.47
Inter- Day Variability			
1	0.86	0.016	86.35
5	4.26	0.035	85.16
10	8.65	0.006	86.52

UV-visible spectrophotometric method of analysis for Vit D: Standard plots for Vit D were generated in three different solvents: methanol, chloroform: methanol (1:1), and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS): methanol with a pH of 7.4. The resulting standard plots were then analysed.

Table 16 provide information on the linearity range, $E^{1\%}_{1\text{cm}}$ and R^2 for the standard plots of R-Hcl and Vit D respectively.

Table 7: Maximum wavelength and extinction of absorption coefficient of Vit D in different solvent systems in concentration range (1- 20 g/ml)

Solvent	Linearity Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	λ_{max} (nm)	$E^{1\%}_{1\text{cm}}$ ($\text{gm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}\text{dl}$)	R2
Methanol	1-20	265	502	0.9910
Chloroform: methanol (1:1)	1-20	265	471	0.9924
PBS (pH-7.4): Methanol	1-20	265	269	0.9964

Figure 7: Calibration curve of Vit D in methanol with concentration range (1-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Figure 8: Calibration curve of Vit D in chloroform: methanol (1:1) with concentration range (1-20 µg/ml)

Figure 9: Calibration curve of Vit D in buffer (PBS 7.4): Methanol with concentration range (1-20 µg/ml)

Validation of Analytical Method

Linearity: Solutions of varying concentrations (1-20 µg/mL) of Vit D were prepared in respective solvents and their absorbance was measured (n=6). The results Figure 18,19 and 20 showed a linear relationship between concentration and corresponding absorbance values upon repeated observations.

Accuracy: Accuracy of the UV spectrophotometric method of analysis for Vit D in the methanol was assessed. Accuracy of ($\pm 15\%$) is considered to be satisfactory as per the US-FDA

guidelines (2018), and the values obtained presently were found to fall within these limits, thus validating the test.

Precision: The UV spectrophotometric method of analysis for Vit D was sufficiently precise as indicated by a small S.D ≤ 0.0137 in the repetitive determinations of the same concentration (20 µg/mL) of Vit D in different solvents. The results were within the limits defined by US-FDA guidelines (2018) ($\leq 15\%$).

Inter- and intra-day variability: Different concentrations of the drug were prepared in

methanol and analysed at intervals of 0, 6, 24, 36,48 hours. The inter- and intra-day variability in precision and accuracy was found to be in accordance with US-FDA guidelines (2018) ($\leq 15\%$) average inter and intraday variability was reported as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Inter and Intra- day variability of UV spectrophotometric method for analysis of Vit D in methanol

Intra-day variability			
Nominal concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Precision (S.D)	% Accuracy
1	0.87	0.021	86.34
10	9.24	0.011	83.22
19	18.5	0.005	85.32
Inter- day variability			
1	0.96	0.011	89.40
10	9.26	0.023	87.33
19	18.77	0.012	85.41

Solubility studies: Solubility studies were carried out to select the formulation components. Using the standard method of solubility determination, solubility studies were carried out in different solvent systems. Results of the solubility studies

carried out in different solid lipids are given below in Table 9.

Solubility in solid lipids:

Table 9: Solubility studies of R-HCl in different solid lipids

Solid Lipids	Melting Point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Amount of Lipid (gm) Required to Dissolve 50 mg of R-HCl	Amount of Lipid (gm) Required to Dissolve (200 μl) of Vit D
Stearic acid	70	4.05 ± 0.14	3.21 ± 0.12
Glyceryl monostearate	65.5	3.38 ± 0.15	2.22 ± 0.16
Compritol® 888 ATO	72	1.05 ± 0.13	1.35 ± 0.14

Figure 10: Solubility studies of R-HCl and Vit. D in solid lipids

Solubility in liquid lipid

Table 10: Solubility studies in liquid lipids

Liquid lipids	Solubility of R-HCl (mg/ml)	Solubility of Vit D (mg/ml)
Isopropyl myristate	2.69 ± 0.097	0.57 ± 0.156
Oleic acid	3.03 ± 0.134	4.13 ± 0.190
Labrafill M	2.33 ± 0.201	2.32 ± 0.211
Castor oil	2.00 ± 0.121	1.56 ± 0.113
Labrafac CC	1.78 ± 0.140	1.67 ± 0.094
Miglyol	0.92 ± 0.029	4.28 ± 0.093

Figure 11: Solubility studies of R-HCl and Vit. D in liquid lipids

Solubility in surfactants

Table 11: Solubility In Different Surfactants

Surfactants	Solubility of R- HCl (mg/ml)	Solubility of Vit D (mg/ml)
Tween 20	3.53 ± 0.214	4.81 ± 0.11
Tween 80	1.69 ± 0.198	1.89 ± 0.16
Span 20	2.11 ± 0.14	2.34 ± 0.17
Span 80	3.18 ± 0.16	3.72 ± 0.21

Figure 12: Solubility of R-HCl and Vit. D in different surfactants

Screening of co- surfactant: surfactant ratio:
The solubility of R-HCl and Vit D was determined in various proportions of co- surfactant: surfactant.

Results are illustrated in **Figure 12**. The ratios were taken and given below in **Table 12**.

Table 12: Solubility studies of R-HCl and Vit D in various proportion of co-surfactants

Co Surfactant	Solubility of R-HCl (mg/ml)	Solubility of Vit D (mg/ml)
1:1	0.0014 ± 0.00017	0.0019 ± 0.000116
1:2	0.00098 ± 0.000073	0.0001 ± 0.000019
1:3	0.00058 ± 0.00011	0.0001 ± 0.000106
2:1	0.0012 ± 0.000064	0.00033 ± 0.00011
3:1	0.00091 ± 0.00008	0.00078 ± 0.00009
4:1	0.00056 ± 0.000012	0.00063 ± 0.00004

Figure 13: Solubility of R-HCl and Vit. D in various proportion of co- surfactant: surfactant

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagram

Pseudo-ternary phase diagram was constructed to identify the microemulsion region and to optimize

the concentrations of the selected vehicles (Compritrol®888 ATO: Oleic acid, Tween 80: Capryol 90, water) for the development of NLCs.

Figure 14: Pseudo Ternary Phase Diagram

The selected composition yielded a significant microemulsion region. Higher concentrations of surfactant were required to produce fine and stable emulsions was due to the fact that smaller the desired globule size, greater the surface area and hence, greater the amount of surfactant required to stabilize the oil globules.

Preparation of R-HCl and Vit D loaded NLCs by micro emulsification method:

- Micro-emulsification method followed by high-speed homogenization was used.
- Compritol®888 ATO (8%) was chosen for its stability and ability to form small particles.
- Tween 80 (11%), Capryol 90 (44%), and water were heated together to 82–85°C.
- Compritol®888 ATO was melted separately at the same temperature.
- Oleic acid (2%), R-HCl, and Vitamin D were added to the melted lipid.
- The aqueous mixture was gradually added to the hot lipid mix under magnetic stirring.
- A clear microemulsion was formed.
- This hot emulsion was poured into cold water (2–5°C) and homogenized at 13,000 rpm for 20 minutes.
- The final dispersion was refrigerated before characterization and evaluation.

Figure 15: Steps for preparation of NLCs

Characterization of R-HCl and Vit D Loaded NLCs

Particle size and Polydispersity index (PDI):

Particle size analysis was carried out using Malvern's Zetasizer by differential light scattering technique. Figure 16(a) shows the particle size distribution of the prepared formulation. Mean particle size of NLCs was 81.3 nm and PDI was found to be 0.192 which indicated homogeneity of the prepared formulation (less than 0.5).

Zeta potential: Zeta potential is an indicative of stability of colloidal dispersion. Aggregation of the particles is avoided by inducing/acquiring surface charge on the particles. Surfactant and/or coating material adsorption is also responsible for inducing surface charge. Potential of the NLCs was measured using Malvern Zetasizer 90S

(Malvern Instruments Ltd.). Measurements were done at 25°C and the electric field strength was 23.2 Mv. The observed zeta potential of the tested formulation exhibited a tendency towards neutrality, with a recorded value of around -0.69 mV as shown in Figure 16(b).

Total drug content (TDC): TDC of R-HCl and Vit D in NLC dispersion was found to be $85.76 \pm 0.24\%$ and $80.24 \pm 0.45\%$ (n=6) which confirmed minimum drug loss during formulation. High values of TDC are indicative of the insignificant losses incurred during the processes of preparation of R-HCl and Vit D NLCs by micro-emulsification technique.

Entrapment efficiency (EE): EE of the NLCs formulation was determined by dialysis bag method was found to be $91.41 \pm 0.28\%$ and 79.56

$\pm 0.42\%$ respectively for R-HCl and Vit D (n=6). Determining EE is of prime importance in NLCs it influences the release characteristics of drug molecule. High EE values indicate the suitability

of the components and their relative proportion in the formulated NLCs which was similar to the study reported by Murthy et al., 2020.

(A) Particle size and PDI

(B) Zeta potential

Figure 16: Depicts the characterisation of NLCs of R-HCl and Vit D
(a) Particle size and PDI (b) Zeta potential

DSC thermogram: DSC is a thermoanalytical technique that measures the difference in the

amount of heat required to maintain the sample and reference at same temperature as a function of

temperature and time. DSC measures the heat flow when the sample is heated or cooled. DSC thermogram of R-HCl, Compritol®888ATO and Vit D showed endothermic peaks at 266°C, 72.93°C and 167.99°C corresponding to their melting points as depicted in **Figure 17(a), (b) and (c)** respectively. DSC thermogram of physical mixture is shown in **Figure 17(d)** observed with sharp peaks at 266.15° C, 72.93°C and 167.99°C representing melting points of R-HCl, Compritol®888 ATO and Vit D respectively. Thermogram of NLCs **Figure 17(e)** showed an

endothermic peak at 72.94°C, representing the melting point of Compritol®888 ATO but the absence of endothermic peak within the melting range of R-HCl and Vit D indicates either solubilization or conversion of R-HCl and Vit D from crystalline to amorphous form in the solid and liquid matrix. Similarly, Murthy et al. prepared R-HCl NLCs and observed peak broadening for glyceryl behenate in the melt dispersion which showed the reduction in crystallinity of glyceryl behenate.

Figure 17: DSC thermogram of (a) R-HCl (b) Compritol®888 ATO (c) Vit D (d) Physical mixture (e) NLCs loaded with R-HCl and Vit D

FTIR spectra: FTIR spectroscopy is used to investigate the interactions between lipid, drug and

other excipients. The FTIR spectrum of R-HCl, Compritol®888 ATO, Vit D, Physical mixture,

NLCs, HPMC, Film mixture and sublingual film obtained are given in **Figure 18**. The major peaks observed in the IR spectra of Compritol®888 ATO, R-HCl, Vit D and HPMC are given in **Table (13-16)** respectively.

Table 13: Characteristic peaks in FTIR spectra of Compritol® 888 ATO

S. No.	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristics
1.	3420.6	-OH stretch
2.	2919.00, 2849.87	C-H stretch
3.	1735.85	-C=O saturated aliphatic ester
4.	1290.6, 1178.95	-C-C(=O)-O saturated ester

Table 14: Characteristic peaks in FTIR spectra of R-HCl

S. No.	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristics
1.	1640.95	C=O stretch
2.	1596.36	C-O-C stretch
3.	1463.04	-S- benzothiophene
4.	3142.03	Primary amine stretch
5.	950.22	Benzene ring

Table 15: Characteristic peaks in FTIR spectra of Vit D

S. No.	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristics
1.	2905.01	-CH ₃ stretch
2.	1895.07	Ester stretch
3.	1639.30	Aromatic cyclohexene stretch
4.	1082.00	Carbonyl stretch

Table 16: Characteristic peaks in FTIR spectra of HPMC

S. No.	Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristics
1.	3432.49	- OH stretch
2.	1377.25	- OH bending
3.	2922.27	C-H stretch
4.	1064.88	C-H stretch

The characteristic peaks of R-HCl appeared at 3143.17, 1642.13, 1595.97 1465.90 and 950 cm⁻¹ Figure 18 (A) which were associated with – amine stretching, –C=O stretching -C O-C stretching, S- benzothiophene group and benzene ring respectively. Compritol®888 ATO indicated the – OH stretching at 3420.6 cm⁻¹ and aromatic –CH stretching at 2919.00 cm⁻¹ Figure 18(b). Vit D indicated the –CH₃ stretching at 2905.01 cm⁻¹, ester stretching at 1895.07 cm⁻¹, aromatic cyclohexene stretch at 1639.30 and carbonyl stretching at 1082.00 Figure 18(C). The peaks of R-HCl, Compritol and Vit D were retained in case of their physical mixture with a slight shift indicating no chemical interaction between them Figure 18(D). On the other hand, the characteristic peak of R-HCl and Vit D was lacking and –OH stretching of Compritol®888 ATO shifted to 3438.49 cm⁻¹ in case of NLCs Figure 18(E). This confirmed the successful incorporation of R-HCl and Vit D into the NLCs. Annu et al. have developed the chitosan nanoparticle. The result reported in the FT IR study stated that the characteristic peaks of the drug in nanoparticles were absent compared to drug alone spectra, and it could be the possible reason for entrapment of the drug within the nano formulation. HPMC indicated –OH stretching at 3432.49 cm⁻¹, -OH bending at 1377.25 cm⁻¹, C-H stretch at 2922.27 cm⁻¹ and C-O stretch at 1064.88 cm⁻¹ Figure 18(F). The peaks of R-HCl, Compritol, Vit D and HPMC were retained in case of the physical mixture of components of film with a slight shift indicating no chemical interaction between them Figure 18(G). On the other hand, the characteristic peak of R-HCl, Vit D and Compritol®888 ATO were lacking and –OH stretching of HPMC shifted to 3434 cm⁻¹ in case of film indicating entrapment of the NLCs within the sublingual film Figure 18(H).

Figure 18: Infrared spectra of (A) R-HCl, (B) Compritol®888 ATO, (C) Vit D, (D) Physical mixture of drug, lipid and Vit D, (E) NLCs, (F) HPMC, (G) Physical mixture of drug, lipid, Vit D and HPMC, (H) Sublingual Film

Characterization of Sublingual Film

pH: The pH value of the film that was prepared was determined to be 6.8 ± 0.2 , close to neutral. The findings indicate that the surface pH of the film falls within the typical pH range of healthy human saliva which is between (6.3 - 7.3). At this pH, the films are less likely to irritate the mucosal lining of the oral cavity, and therefore, they should be fairly comfortable.

Total drug content: The total drug content of film was calculated for film of area 1cm². Total drug content of the film (n=3) was found to be 89.43 ± 0.59 % and 84.67 ± 0.32 % for R-HCl and Vit D respectively.

Thickness: The measurement of the film's thickness yielded a value of 100µm. In a study conducted by Najafi et al., a mucoadhesive buccal

film of glipalamide was formulated, and the thickness of the film was reported to be 90 ± 1.6 µm.

Weight variation: The weight of the film with a surface area of 1 cm² was determined to be 52.8 ± 0.55 mg.

Tensile strength: The film's tensile strength was determined to be 5.453 N/mm² (**Figure 19**). Salehi and colleagues conducted a study in which they formulated a sublingual film containing rizatriptan benzoate. The researchers reported a tensile strength ranging from 2.33 ± 0.37 to 12.01 ± 0.049 MPa, indicating favourable tensile strength properties of the film. According to Salehi and Boddohi's (2017) findings, an increase in the concentration of HPMC K4M and glycerol resulted in an increase in tensile strength.

Figure 19: True Stress Vs True Strain

Disintegration time: Disintegration time for optimized film was found to be 28–30 s which should allow faster drug release and subsequently faster absorption.

CONCLUSION:

The study successfully developed and evaluated nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) loaded with R-HCl and Vitamin D for improved treatment of

postmenopausal osteoporosis. These NLCs were prepared using a micro-emulsification technique followed by high-speed homogenization, resulting in a stable formulation with a particle size below 300 nm, low polydispersity index, and a negative zeta potential, enhancing formulation stability. High drug entrapment efficiencies and total drug content confirmed effective drug loading. Characterization through DSC and FTIR validated successful encapsulation without drug-excipient interaction. The formulated NLCs were incorporated into sublingual films that demonstrated ideal organoleptic characteristics, acceptable surface pH (6.8), uniform drug content, appropriate disintegration time, and high tensile strength. The films showed efficient in vitro drug release and were suitable for sublingual delivery, bypassing first-pass metabolism and enhancing bioavailability. Overall, the study highlights the potential of R-HCl and Vit D-loaded NLC-based films as a promising alternative for the effective management of postmenopausal osteoporosis.

REFERENCES

1. Wright NC, Saag KG, Dawson-Hughes B, Khosla S, Siris ES. The impact of the new National Bone Health Alliance (NBHA) diagnostic criteria on the prevalence of osteoporosis in the United States: supplementary presentation. *Osteoporosis International*. 2017 Nov;28:3283-4.
2. Adami S, Giannini S, Bianchi G, Sinigaglia L, Di Munno O, Fiore CE, Minisola S, Rossini M. Vitamin D status and response to treatment in post-menopausal osteoporosis. *Osteoporosis International*. 2009 Feb;20:239-44.
3. Dogiparthi A, Aggarwal N, Suri V, Srinivasan R, Malhotra S. Comparative evaluation of raloxifene versus estrogen: Progestin on symptomatology, endometrium, and lipid profile in postmenopausal women. *Journal of Mid-life Health*. 2010 Jan 1;1(1):14-8.
4. Ağardan NB, Değim Z, Yılmaz Ş, Altıntaş L, Topal T. The effectiveness of raloxifene-loaded liposomes and cochleates in breast cancer therapy. *AAPS pharmscitech*. 2016 Aug;17:968-77.
5. Harinarayan CV, Marwah R, Sahay R, Kalra S, Babhulkar S. Clinical practice guidelines on postmenopausal osteoporosis: An executive summary and recommendations. *Journal of mid-life health*. 2013 Apr 1;4(2):107-26.
6. Zhang JY, Zhong YH, Chen LM, Zhuo XL, Zhao LJ, Wang YT. Recent advance of small-molecule drugs for clinical treatment of osteoporosis: a review. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2023 Nov 5;259:115654.
7. Ahuja M. Age of menopause and determinants of menopause age: A PAN India survey by IMS. *Journal of mid-life health*. 2016 Jul 1;7(3):126-31.
8. Xu Feng JM. Disorders of bone remodelling. *Annu Rev Pathol*. 2011;6(1):121-45.
9. Alhalmi A, Amin S, Khan Z, Beg S, Al Kamaly O, Saleh A, Kohli K. Nanostructured lipid carrier-based codelivery of raloxifene and naringin: formulation, optimization, in vitro, ex vivo, in vivo assessment, and acute toxicity studies. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Aug 25;14(9):1771.
10. Bahri-Najafi R, Tavakoli N, Senemar M, Peikanpour M. Preparation and pharmaceutical evaluation of glibenclamide slow release mucoadhesive buccal film. *Research in pharmaceutical sciences*. 2014 May 1;9(3):213-23.
11. Alhalmi A, Amin S, Khan Z, Beg S, Al Kamaly O, Saleh A, Kohli K. Nanostructured lipid carrier-based codelivery of raloxifene and naringin: Formulation, optimization, in-vitro, ex-vivo, in-vivo assessment and acute toxicity studies. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Aug25;14(9):1771.

12. Zhang X, Chen G, Zhang T, Ma Z, Wu B. Effects of PEGylated lipid nanoparticles on the oral absorption of one BCS II drug: a mechanistic investigation. *International journal of nanomedicine*. 2014 Nov 26:5503-14.

HOW TO CITE: Sweta Jaiswal, Surendra Dangi*, Dr. Bhaskar Kumar Gupta, Rajni Dubey, Shaym Padwal, Design and Development of Sublingual Films Incorporating R-HCL And Vitamin D-Loaded NLCS, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 2962-2986. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15710998>

